

Evaluating Professional Development Needs of Secondary School Teachers for Improved Learning Outcomes in Sindh: A Mixed Method Study

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ABSTRACT: Assessment and evaluation play a pivotal role in the secondary school teachers' professional development. The Present study aims at to explore Sindh Secondary Education Improvement Project (SSEIP), to assess and improve the professional competencies of secondary school teachers in Sindh specifically in five core subjects: English, Biology, Chemistry, Physics, and Mathematics. The study used mixed methods of research design to examine teachers' assessment, subject-specific expertise, pedagogical skills and content-based knowledge. The Likert based questionnaire was constructed, and an interview protocol were carried out from the study sample size 511 secondary school teachers in the 05 subjects: English, Mathematics, Physics, Chemistry, Biology Grades 9- 10 from Rural SBA and Urban Karachi. Moreover, the study tries to integrate the four main domains National Professional Standards for Teachers (NPST): Use of ICT, Assessment, Instructional Planning and Strategies, and Human Growth and Development. The study results reveal that there is significant gaps in teachers' professional training, subject-matter expertise, and understanding pedagogical frameworks, especially constructivist teaching, inclusive practices, assessment literacy, and ICT integration. The study also found that the deficiencies in both male and female cohorts, according to gender-disaggregated data. The study recommended that the teachers should emphasizing on subject mastery and pedagogical innovation for recruitment standards, capacity-building modules, and policy reforms that will help to achieve SDG 4 and enhance secondary school learning outcomes. Finally, the study recommended that the same study can be conducted at the college level to develop teachers professional and pedagogical development in assessment and evaluation.

Key words: Professional development, Secondary school teachers, Learning outcomes, Evaluation

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1. Introduction

Teacher quality is a fundamental determinant of student achievement and the overall effectiveness of the education system. In the context of developing countries like Pakistan, professional development of teachers is increasingly recognized as instrumental for

educational reform (Yangambi, 2021; Merritt et al., 2019). Numerous studies emphasize that Continuous Professional Development (CPD) significantly enhances teachers' pedagogical approaches, subject knowledge, and assessment literacy (Bubb, 2004; Macià & García, 2016; Depaepe & König, 2018).

Ghunio, Niamatullah, and Shaikh (2023) conducted a mixed-method study in Sukkur, Sindh, which revealed that CPD has a statistically significant impact on improving teaching approaches and student outcomes. Regression analysis showed a strong positive relationship ($\beta = 0.269$, $p < 0.05$), emphasizing the need for systemic support for CPD programs in Pakistan. Similarly, Soomro, Zamir, and Soomro (2025) assessed teacher training quality in North Sindh and identified key gaps, including the absence of contextualized assessment frameworks and feedback systems, which hinder effective professional growth.

The Asian Development Bank (2023) further stresses the urgent need for deploying qualified subject specialists, strengthening ICT integration, and enhancing institutional capacity for both pre-service and in-service teacher training. These priorities echo the TNA findings, which indicated that many secondary-level science and mathematics teachers held academic degrees in unrelated fields like arts or Islamic studies.

Ahmed and Suhag (2024) explored the institutional practices of academic coordinators in facilitating CPD for primary school teachers. Their findings highlighted that peer coaching, online learning, and collaborative methods significantly improved teaching practices, but were hindered by low teacher motivation, lack of time, and limited resources. The study by Balal et al. (2022) reinforced the notion that effective professional development is need-based and should align with teachers' career growth aspirations. Guskey (2000) described PD as a systematic process to enhance educators' professional knowledge and attitudes—a perspective echoed by multiple empirical studies linking teacher knowledge to instructional quality and student performance (König & Pflanzl, 2016; Voss et al., 2011)

According to reports, Sindh has Pakistan's second-lowest net and gross enrollment rates across all educational levels. The dearth of excellent teacher education programs is one of the main causes of the poor educational results. The goal of the 2005-launched Strengthening Teacher Education in Pakistan (STEP) project was to increase the government's ability to guarantee high-quality teacher education. The National Professional Standards for Teachers (NPST) were developed by the Ministry of Education in partnership with UNESCO and with funding from USAID. However, a recent 2020 study revealed that while the majority of teacher educators agreed that NPST was suitable for offering a framework and benchmarks for teacher education, it had not yet been fully implemented in teacher The present study focused on four standards of NPST, namely Standard-2 Human Growth and Development (HGD), Standard-4 Instructional Planning and Strategies (IPS), Standard-5 Assessment and Standard-7 Use of Information Communication Technology. The subject specific pedagogical content knowledge, subject specific content knowledge and awareness of global local policy context were also explored.

Research Objectives:

RO1. To Determine the current academic and professional qualification profile of secondary school teachers in Sindh teaching English, Mathematics, Physics, Chemistry, and Biology

RO2. To examine the secondary school teachers' competencies in key areas defined by the National Professional Standards for Teachers (NPST), particularly in Human Growth and Development (Standard 2), Instructional Planning and Strategies (Standard 4), Assessment (Standard 5), and Use of ICT (Standard 7) in Sindh

RO3. To Compare the teachers' perceptions and experiences, about their professional development needs, and the challenges they face in delivering subject-specific instruction? How adequate are they in addressing instructional, assessment, and content-related needs,

Research Questions:

RQ1. What is the current academic and professional qualification profile of secondary school teachers in Sindh teaching English, Mathematics, Physics, Chemistry, and Biology?

RQ2. To what extent are secondary school teachers competent in key areas defined by the National Professional Standards for Teachers (NPST), particularly in Human Growth and Development (Standard 2), Instructional Planning and Strategies (Standard 4), Assessment (Standard 5), and Use of ICT (Standard 7) in Sindh?

RQ3. What are teachers' perceptions and experiences, about their professional development needs, and the challenges they face in delivering subject-specific instruction? How adequate are they in addressing instructional, assessment, and content-related needs?

Research Hypothesis:

RH1. There is no significant difference in the academic and professional qualification profiles of secondary school teachers in Sindh teaching English, Mathematics, Physics, Chemistry, and Biology subjects.

RH2: There is no significant competence demonstrated by secondary school teachers in Sindh in the NPST standards related to Human Growth and Development, Instructional Planning and Strategies, Assessment, and Use of ICT.

H3: There is no significant relationship between the adequacy of professional development and teachers' perceived challenges in delivering subject-specific instruction or their preparedness to address instructional, assessment, and content-related needs.

2. Methodology

The mixed-method research design uses to examine the secondary school teachers' competencies in key areas defined by the National Professional Standards for Teachers. The list of survey participants was prepared by distributing samples among the divisions and by selecting the sampled teachers from the already nominated 2360 teacher list, the Stratified Random Sampling technique was used and cross-sectional survey was conducted from 5 11

teachers among the 05 subjects and gender teacher 72 male and female secondary teachers in English, Mathematics, Physics, Chemistry, Biology Grades 9- 10 from Rural SBA and Urban Karachi. After data entry and cleaning for missing values, vague, and over-written responses, the data of 65 teachers comprising of 31(47%) female teachers and 34(53%) male teachers was analyzed for internal consistency of the capacity assessment questionnaire and each of the 9 subscales for internal consistency using Cronbach's alpha reliability technique whereas in the qualitative part focus group discussion or an interview was conducted from secondary school teachers. The tool was developed through a detailed literature review of various TNA research methodologies, educational policies, gender frameworks and reports, SESLOAF, assessment frameworks, research articles on Technological pedagogical and content knowledge (TPACK), TPACK Questionnaires. For Pedagogical content knowledge (PCK) and learning approaches, National Professional Standards for Teachers (NPST) in Pakistan, National and Provincial Curriculum documents were undertaken to develop a proposal, comprehensive framework, scales and indicators. Using a Proportional Stratified Random Sampling. A sample comprising of a total of 511 were selected to be surveyed after equally distributing among the 5 subjects and gender. The Capacity and Needs assessment survey too was self-administered by qualified and trained field staff, and data was collected from the teachers selected from the already received nominations of 2630 teachers. However, considering that some districts had a very limited number of nominated teachers, more than one district per division were selected for the survey to capture the total sample.

3. Discussion

A swift mode was adopted by the Field Staff (Managers, Supervisors and Enumerators) making individual calls to every teacher on the list and through the head teachers, to inform the research participants of the survey purpose, date and venue. After communicating with the teachers, the Survey was conducted in all the districts at the venues provided by the DEO offices (the Government of Sindh).

Quantitative data was entered by trained data entry operators in the designed Kobo Toolbox application and constantly monitored to avoid any data entry errors. The data entered was exported to excel sheets and then categorized into tables according to the sections in the questionnaire, scales, sub-scales and indicators. Specific counts, averages and percentages tables, charts, pie and bar-graphs were later generated. The digitally recorded qualitative data was transcribed and translated by specialized transcribers, next, coding and thematic analysis were undertaken. In the next section the data is described, findings, analysis are presented based on the study objectives and recommendations are made particularly for the program and in general for secondary English, Mathematics, Physics, Chemistry, and Biology teachers.

Data Analysis and Implications

This section presents the Findings and Analysis of the surveyed teachers' location, gender, academic and professional background and years of teaching experience as secondary school biology, chemistry, physics, mathematics and English teachers.

A.1. Availability of Biology, Chemistry, Physics, Mathematics and English Teachers in Districts: Findings and Analysis.

The table 1 indicates district-wise distributions of teachers sampled using proportionate random sampling from the district-wise nominated list for training of teachers teaching biological, chemical and physical sciences, mathematics and English, including a total of 469 teachers, and a maximum of 181 from Hyderabad and a minimum of 37 from Sukkur Division.

This reflects that biology, chemistry, physics, mathematics and English subject teachers at secondary levels are available in all districts, but the number is not consistent. However, the distribution is based on the list of nominated population and may not be representative of the actual district-based population of teachers teaching biological sciences at secondary levels in Sindh.

Recommendations:

There is a need to ascertain the data of all teachers to identify the availability of teachers of all subjects and genders at district levels.

Table 1: District-wise Representation of Sampled Teachers.

Count of Subject	Subject					Grand Total
Subjects	Biology	Chemistry	English	Math	Physics	Grand Total
Hyderabad	37	33	44	33	34	181
Karachi	8	7	9	11	7	42
Larkana	11	8	13	11	5	48
Mirpurkhas	19	14	16	21	16	86
SBA	15	16	12	16	16	75
Sukkur	7	8	8	7	7	37
Grand Total	97	86	102	99	85	469

A.2 Gender Representation: Findings and Analysis.

The table 2 data disclose that the overall sample comprised 220 female teachers, 244 male teachers, and five participants did not provide a response. The distribution of male and female teachers in the sample is relatively balanced, with a slight numerical advantage for male teachers. The presence of only five no-response also indicates a high level of response rate and participant engagement.

Table 2: Gender Representation Recommendations:

Subject	Gender			Grand Total
	Male	Female	No Response	
Biology	52	44	1	97
Chemistry	46	39	1	86
English	49	53		102
Math	51	47	1	99
Physics	46	37	2	85
Grand Total	244	220	5	469

The program design is required to address the unique needs and preferences of both male and female teachers, fostering an inclusive learning environment. The program should strengthen efforts to encourage participation and consider incorporating additional strategies to promote diversity and inclusion, ensuring that all teachers from urban and rural areas attend the program, actively contribute to and benefit from the program.

Figure: Gender and Age Distribution

The gender and age distribution indicates that most of the female teachers (149 teachers) are in the age group 20-40 years, whereas most of the male teachers (142 teachers) are in the age group 31-50 years. Furthermore, there are 21 Female and 43 Male teachers, i.e. 64 teachers, 13.6% of the teachers that are above 50 years of age in the sampled teachers. This indicates that the teachers are of varied age groups from 20 years to 50 years and above.

Recommendations

The results emphasize the necessity of scrutinizing the list of teachers who have been nominated and acquiring fresh nominations for educators who are over 50. Due to their impending retirement and short tenure, these educators might not have much of an impact on the system.

A.4. Academic Qualification: Findings and Analysis:

The data on the academic qualifications of the sampled Teachers indicates that most of the teachers 96% have a matriculation in science and 38% have a master's in science. The data indicates a decline of teachers with qualifications in sciences at master's level. This indicates a lack of relevant and adequate higher level content knowledge of the sampled science teachers.

Table 3: Academic Qualification Matriculation

Academic Qualification Matriculation						
Subject	Teachers	Arts	Science	Computer Science	No Response	Grand Total
Biology		1	94	1	1	97
Chemistry			85		1	86
English		1	97	2	2	102
Math		1	95	3		99
Physics		1	81	2	1	85
Grand Total		4	452	8	5	469

Table 4: Academic Qualification Masters

Academic Qualifications: Academic Qualification: Masters						
Subjects	Biology Teachers	Chemistry Teachers	English Teachers	Mathematics Teachers	Physics Teachers	Grand Total
Arts	27	17	63	38	22	167
Science	40	57	15	32	35	179
Commerce/Business Administration	6	2	6	3	2	19
No Response	19	5	16	24	23	87
Others	5	5	2	2	3	17
Grand Total	97	86	102	99	85	469

This decline could raise concerns about the depth of content knowledge among teachers. The decreasing percentage of teachers with advanced degrees (Bachelor's and Master's) may signify a potential lack of in-depth content knowledge. This is crucial in teaching advanced scientific concepts and keeping up with advancements in the field.

Recommendations

The program should concentrate on improving teachers' content knowledge, particularly for those who lack a science bachelor's or master's degree. To address the noted drop in the proportion of teachers with bachelor's and master's degrees, the program should create and incorporate subject-specific sessions in significant and updated content. To build a solid foundation in subject matter knowledge and up-to-date knowledge, a subject matter knowledge module will be necessary. The above-mentioned conclusions are supported by the qualitative data, which shows that teachers with academic backgrounds in the arts, languages, Islamic culture, and economics were instructing students in mathematics and science.

Thematic Analysis: Teachers teaching higher and secondary sciences and mathematics with Masters in Arts, Economics, Islamic Culture and Languages:

The qualitative data further supports the findings that the teachers currently teaching physics, chemistry, biological and chemical sciences have Bachelors and master's in arts, Economics, Islamic Culture and Languages. "Dadoo Mal (Pseudonym): HST from government high school Amroto personally I am HST, but I teach biology, I think it is last ten years.

Interviewer: Qualification, what is your qualification?

Dadoo Mal: B.A B.Ed.". "Sharik (Pseudonym): I am not biology teacher I teach mathematics, ok, and by the way I have done Masters in Sindhi.

Interviewer: Masters in Sindhi and you are teaching mathematics?

Sharik: DEO office has nominated me for Biology, I have been teaching math for the last five years.

Interviewer: And you are qualified as MA in Sindhi?

Sharik: Yes.

Interviewer: So, you don't have a degree related to math's and you teach math's?

[Anonymous]: I teach math's till matric classes.

Interviewer: You teach math's up to matric classes!"

Teacher 1: My name is M. Saeed. My age is between 45 and 50 years and I have been teaching biology since last 1 year. My highest qualification is Masters in Urdu

Teacher 2: Syed Majid Ali, my age is 45 years. I have done MA in English Literature. Have been teaching Biology for five years.

Teacher 3: My name is Muhammad Tariq, and I am 25 years old.

Teaching biology for the last 3 to 4 months. I have done bachelor's in economics.

Teacher 4: My name is Aliya Memon. I am HST. I teach Chemistry at Government Girls School Qasimabad. I was transferred here five years ago and since then I have been teaching Chemistry to class 9. I am 53 years old. I have done MA in Islamic Culture. This is my academic degree and I also have an M Ed.

A.5. Professional Qualification: Findings and Analysis:

The data on professional qualifications is mixed, it indicates that 326 teachers i.e. 69.5% of the teachers have some professional qualifications. Among these, around 73 teachers i.e. 15.5 % have a 4-year B.Ed. degree and 94 teachers possess a master's qualification. A significant portion of teachers, 143 (30%) teaching at the secondary level, do not possess any professional qualification. This is concerning as professional qualifications play a crucial role in ensuring effective teaching practice and improved learning outcomes. Only 20% of teachers possess a master's qualification. This is a relatively low percentage and may indicate a shortage of teachers with advanced academic and pedagogical training at secondary levels in the system.

Table 5: Professional Qualification

All professional qualification										
Row Labels	PT C	CT C	B.Ed. (Year not mentioned)	B.Ed. (1 Year)	B.Ed. (1.5 Years)	B.Ed. (2 Years)	B.Ed. (4 Years)	M.Ed.	M Phil in Education	None of the Above
Biology	2	11	25	4	22	21	23	2	42	
Chemistry	5	9	2	22	22	21	2	50	1	15
English	5	20	17	7	23	27	27	4	51	2
Math	9	13	20	4	24	30	19	2	46	
Physics	4	8	1	28	20	18	2	36	1	16
Grand Total	25	61	65	65	111	117	73	94	141	33

Recommendations:

Given the diverse professional qualifications among teachers, encompassing, 1 to 4 years of B.Ed. and M.Ed., and 30% lacking professional qualifications, it is pertinent to implement a comprehensive foundational module covering general pedagogical skills and learning approaches, curriculum planning, assessment strategies, classroom management, and gender-sensitive techniques. Additionally, an advanced module focusing on subject-specific pedagogical content knowledge is essential. This dual approach aims to equip teachers with both general pedagogical skills standards and specific teaching skills, IPS and HD standards outlined in the National Teachers Standards and specific pedagogical content knowledge.

At the policy level, it is crucial to reconsider the recruitment policy for secondary levels. The emphasis should shift towards employing teachers with a 4-year B.Ed. qualification, or alternatively, implementing on-the-job qualifications to ensure continued employment and career progression. Encouraging the acquisition of professional qualifications for teaching at all levels is vital for enhancing the overall quality of education. Addressing these aspects is pivotal in establishing a more robust and effective educational system.

A.6. Experience: Findings and Analysis:

The teaching experience of the sampled teachers varies across different positions. There are 64 teachers with 1-10 years of primary teaching experience. A significant number of teachers (332) have experience as Junior Elementary School Teachers (JEST). Whereas 272 teachers have experience as Higher Secondary School Teachers (HST) and Only 41 teachers have experience as subject specialists. The low number of teachers (41) with subject specialist teaching experience indicates a potential imbalance in specialized expertise within the teaching staff.

Recommendations:

The teaching experience data in table 6 , indicates that 272 teachers have HST experience and as HST is attained through promotion, and not subject specialization, this indicates a very low number of teachers with subject specialization. Also, as only 38% of the sampled Science teachers have a master's in sciences, hence there is a lack of specialized subject matter knowledge. The program needs to develop and offer modules to enhance subject matter/content knowledge of teachers to be able to teach at grades 9-10 levels.

Table 6: Teaching Experience

Designation	1-10 years	11-20 years	21-30 years	Above 30 years	no response	Total
PST	64	2	4	0	399	469
JEST	281	31	20	0	137	469
HST	198	45	20	9	197	469
SST	36	2	3	0	428	469

A.7. Professional Development Experience: Findings and Analysis:

The data on prior professional development experience indicates that most of the teachers 167 i.e. 35.6% have received induction training, the second most common training received by teachers were Life Skills Based Education, including a component on “Bad and Good Touch”. Few teachers have received SESLOAF training, SAT, Health, Oral Health, TB, Child Abuse, Scouting, Flood, STEM and ECE.

Recommendations:

The responses indicate that the teachers have not received any subject specific content, general and specific pedagogical content knowledge, learning approaches and gender sensitive strategies focused on professional development and hence a need to develop and offer a program on specific higher secondary level content, instructional and assessment strategies, use of technology and gender inclusive strategies.

1. Identify the gap between prevailing levels of knowledge on Standard-2 Human Growth and Development (HGD), Standard-4 Instructional Planning and Strategies (IPS), Standard-5 Assessment, Standard-7 Use of Information Communication Technology and the required level prescribed in the professional standards.

This section found the gaps between prevailing levels of Knowledge and skills of Standard 2, 4, 5 and 7. Knowledge and skills on Standard-2 Human Growth and Development (HGD) was explored through 9 indicators, based on knowledge of Constructivism and Conceptual Change, Behaviorism, Inclusive Learning and Diversified learning approaches, Engagement, Enjoyment, Creativity, Curiosity and Real-life Problem Solving.

The responses indicate that 69 % of the teachers have not heard either, have not received training and are unskilled in Constructivism and Conceptual Change, whereas a lower percentage 31% are confident and skilled. 74% are unskilled in Behaviorism and 26% are confident and skilled, which indicates that some teachers are applying transmission modes of teaching. 70 % of teachers have never heard and are unskilled in Inclusive Learning and Diversified Learning approaches, whereas 30 % of teachers are skilled and confident. 70

% of teachers have never heard of and are unskilled in learning approaches to promote engagement, enjoyment, creativity, curiosity, and real-life problem solving, whereas 30 % reported that they are skilled and confident. The low percentage of skilled teachers in standard 2 is very concerning and indicates the prevalence of rote memorization and transmission approaches to teaching in the system.

The Knowledge and skills on Standard-4 instructional Planning and Strategies was explored through 15 indicators for general pedagogical skills and 8 indicators for content specific pedagogical content knowledge. The self-reported data indicates that a concerning percentage 72% of the teachers have never heard of it and are unskilled whereas, a lower percentage 28% are confident and have applied Instructional Planning and Strategies. The self-reported data indicates that a concerning 75% of teachers have no knowledge and are unskilled in context specific pedagogical knowledge and a lower percentage 25% are confident and skilled.

The Knowledge and skills on Standard-5 Assessment was explored through 9 indicators, 2 indicators were related on Blooms Taxonomy and Higher order thinking questions, 6 indicators were related to types of assessments and 1 indicator explored the use of marking rubrics. The self-reported data on knowledge and skills related to Blooms Taxonomy and higher order thinking questions indicates that a concerning number 80% of the teachers have never heard, used, hence have no knowledge and were unskilled and a significantly lower number 20% were have had training, were confident and skilled.

The self-reported data on knowledge and skills related types of assessments indicates that concerning 79% of the teachers have never heard, have never used, hence have no knowledge and are unskilled and a significantly lower number 21% have had training, are confident and skilled. The self-reported data on knowledge and skills related to use of rubric indicates that a concerning 82% of the teachers have never heard, used, hence have no knowledge and were unskilled and a significantly lower number 18 % have had training, were confident and skilled.

The knowledge and skills on Standard-7 Use of Information Communication Technology was explored through 8 indicators. The self-reported data indicates that a concerning 89 % have never heard, have never used, have no knowledge and are unskilled and a significantly lower number 11% have had training, are confident and skilled in the use of Information Communication Technology.

Insinuations:

The above findings imply that a concerning high percentage of the sampled teachers have never heard, have never used, hence have no knowledge and are unskilled in the above NPST, namely Standard-2 Human Growth and Development (HGD), Standard-4 Instructional Planning and Strategies (IPS), Standard-5 Assessment and Standard-7 Use of Information Communication Technology, hence the program needs to include these to build the teachers competency in these standards.

2. Determine the difference between knowledge/skills in Standard-2 Human Growth and Development (HGD), Standard-4 Instructional Planning and Strategies (IPS), Standard-5 on Assessment, Standard-7 on Use of Information Communication Technology of male and

female teachers teaching secondary classes in the project target districts and six divisions of Sindh.

This section found the gaps between prevailing levels of Knowledge and skills of female and male teachers on Standard 2, 4, 5 and 7. The Knowledge and skills on Standard-2 Human Growth and Development (HGD) was explored through 9 indicators, based on knowledge of Constructivism and Conceptual Change, Behaviorism, Inclusive Learning and Diversified learning approaches, Engagement, Enjoyment, Creativity, Curiosity and Real-life Problem Solving.

This section presents the prevailing levels of knowledge and skills on Standard-2 Human Growth and Development (HGD). The responses indicate that 67 % of the female teachers have either not heard, have not received training and are unskilled in Constructivism and Conceptual Change, whereas a lower percentage 33% are confident and skilled. 74% of the female teachers are unskilled in Behaviorism and 26 % are confident and skilled, which indicates that some teachers are applying transmission modes of teaching. 69 % of the female teachers have never heard and are unskilled in Inclusive Learning and Diversified learning approaches, whereas 31% of the female teachers are skilled and confident. 68 % of the female teachers have never heard and are unskilled in learning approaches to promote engagement, enjoyment, creativity, curiosity, and real-life problem solving, whereas 32 % of the female teachers self-reported that they are skilled and confident. The low percentage of skilled female teachers in standard 2 is very concerning and indicates the prevalence of rote memorization and transmission approaches to teaching in the system.

This section presents the prevailing levels of knowledge and skills on Standard-2 Human Growth and Development (HGD). The responses indicate that 72 % of the male teachers have either not heard, have not received training and are unskilled in Constructivism and Conceptual Change, whereas a lower percentage 28% are confident and skilled. 74% of the male teachers have either not heard, have not received training and are unskilled in Behaviorism and 26 % are confident and skilled, which indicates that some teachers are applying transmission modes of teaching. 71 % of male teachers have never heard and are unskilled in Inclusive Learning and Diversified learning approaches, whereas 29% of the female teachers are skilled and confident. 74 % of the male teachers have never heard and are unskilled in learning approaches to promote engagement, enjoyment, creativity, curiosity, and real-life problem solving, whereas 36 % of the male teachers self-reported that they are skilled and confident. The low percentage of skilled male teachers in standard 2 is very concerning and indicates the prevalence of rote memorization and transmission approaches to teaching in the system.

The Knowledge and skills on Standard-4 instructional Planning and Strategies was explored through 15 indicators for general pedagogical skills and 8 indicators for content specific pedagogical content knowledge. The self-reported data indicates that a concerning percentage 73% of the male teachers have never heard of it and are unskilled whereas, a lower percentage 27% are confident and have applied Instructional Planning and Strategies. The self-reported data indicates that a concerning 74% of male teachers have no knowledge and are unskilled in content specific pedagogical content knowledge and a lower percentage 26% are confident and skilled.

The Knowledge and skills on Standard-4 instructional Planning and Strategies was explored through 15 indicators for general pedagogical skills and 8 indicators for content specific pedagogical content knowledge. The self-reported data indicates that a concerning percentage 71% of the female teachers have never heard of it and are unskilled whereas, a lower percentage 29% are confident and have applied Instructional Planning and Strategies. The self-reported data indicates that a concerning 76% of female teachers have no knowledge and are unskilled in content specific pedagogical content knowledge and a lower percentage 24% are confident and skilled.

The Knowledge and skills on Standard-5 Assessment was explored through 9 indicators, 2 indicators were related on Blooms Taxonomy and Higher order thinking questions, 6 indicators were related to types of assessments and 1 indicator explored the use of marking rubrics. The self-reported data on knowledge and skills related to Blooms Taxonomy and higher order thinking questions indicates that a concerning 80% of the female teachers have never heard, used, hence have no knowledge and were unskilled and a significantly lower number 20% have had training, were confident and skilled.

The self-reported data on knowledge and skills related to Blooms Taxonomy and higher order thinking questions indicates that a concerning 81% of the **male** teachers have never heard, used, hence have no knowledge and were unskilled and a significantly lower number 19% have had training, were confident and skilled. The self-reported data on knowledge and skills related types of assessments indicates that a concerning 78% of the female teachers have never heard, have never used, hence have no knowledge and are unskilled and a significantly lower number 22% have had training, are confident and skilled. The self-reported data on knowledge and skills related to use of rubric indicates that a concerning 82% of the female teachers have never heard, used, hence have no knowledge and were unskilled and a significantly lower number 18 % have had training, were confident and skilled.

The self-reported data on knowledge and skills related types of assessments indicates that a concerning 79% of the male teachers have never heard, have never used, hence have no knowledge and are unskilled and a significantly lower number 21% have had training, are confident and skilled. The self-reported data on knowledge and skills related to use of rubric indicates that a concerning 82% of the male teachers have never heard, used, hence have no knowledge and were unskilled and a significantly lower number 18 % have had training, were confident and skilled.

The knowledge and skills on Standard-7 Use of Information Communication Technology was explored through 8 indicators. The self-reported data indicates that a concerning 89 % of the female teachers have never heard, have never used, hence have no knowledge and are unskilled and a significantly lower number 11% have had training, are confident and skilled in the use of Information Communication Technology. The knowledge and skills on Standard-7 Use of Information Communication Technology was explored through 8 indicators. The self-reported data indicates that a concerning 88 % of the male teachers have never heard, have never used, hence have no knowledge and are unskilled and a significantly lower number 12% have had training, are confident and skilled in the use of Information Communication Technology.

Insinuations

The above findings imply that a concerning high percentage of the sampled female and male teachers have never heard, have never used, hence have no knowledge and are unskilled in the above NPST, namely Standard-2 Human Growth and Development (HGD), Standard-4 Instructional Planning and Strategies (IPS), Standard-5 Assessment and Standard-7 Use of Information Communication Technology, hence the program needs to include these to build the teachers competency in these standards for the improvement of teaching and learning at grade 9 and 10 levels.

4. Conclusion

In conclusion, the quality of teachers has a significant impact on both the effectiveness of the educational system and the achievement of students' learning objectives. The deficiencies outlined in the Training Needs Assessment (TNA) study must be systematically addressed in order to improve educational systems and achieve Sustainable Development Goal 4 (SDG 4). This calls for a diligent pursuit of thorough mastery of relevant subjects like Human Growth and Development (HGD), Instructional Planning and Strategies (IPS), Assessment techniques, and the skillful application of Information and Communication Technology (ICT). Furthermore, teachers' development of strong Subject Matter/Content knowledge, especially in the areas of English, Biology, Chemistry, Physics, and Mathematics, deserves special attention, with an emphasis on both best practices and opportunities for growth. Educational stakeholders can create an atmosphere that supports excellence and ongoing development in teacher preparation and classroom instruction by giving priority to these measures, which will promote comprehensive educational advancement across the Sindh.

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